

Design, layout and simulation of 3T-APS pixels using the Open Sky130 Process Design Kit

Luís Karlos Oliveira
Faculdade de Engenharia
Universidade Federal de Juiz de Fora
Juiz de Fora – MG, Brazil
luis.karlos@estudante.ufjf.br

Estêvão Coelho Teixeira
Faculdade de Engenharia
Universidade Federal de Juiz de Fora
Juiz de Fora – MG, Brazil
estevao.teixeira@ufjf.br

Filipe Santos
Vinci Consulting
F-91192 Gif-sur-Yvette, France
filipe@laposte.net

Abstract—The Active Pixel Sensor (APS) is the core of modern CMOS imagers, which are currently present in almost all image acquisition applications. The key structure of an APS pixel is constructed using a photosensitive block and three readout transistors, known as the 3T pixel. Based on a previous work, this paper describes the design, layout and extracted circuit simulation of four different readout circuits, using different MOSFET devices available from the open Sky130 Process Design Kit (PDK). The conversion gain and transient responses from each of the four pixels are compared, w.r.t. the output voltage swing, showing that open-source tools and this open PDK can be successfully employed on optimizing the design of this key sensor technology.

Index Terms—CMOS image sensor, Active Pixel Sensor, Open PDKs, Sky130, Open Source Tools.

I. INTRODUCTION

Since the 1990s, CMOS imagers have been intensively researched, driven by the demand for portable, low-power, and miniaturized imaging systems [1]. Active Pixel Sensors (APS) are the fundamental elements of CMOS imagers, and the great advantage of APS CMOS technology is the integration of the sensor and all the readout electronics (all the analog, digital control, digitization, and processing) into a single chip. Numerous publications have reported improvements in several limitations of APS technology, such as noise reduction [2], increased dynamic range [3], and the use of in-pixel processing [4].

The basic APS pixel has, in addition to a photosensitive element, three MOSFETs working as an analog readout circuit (3T pixel). Better performance can be obtained by adding a transmission gate transistor, leading to the 4T pixel [5], but this requires a kind of transistor not available in standard CMOS fabrication technology such as SkyWater Sky130 targeted by the open Sky130 Process Design Kit (PDK) [6]. Nonetheless, 3T pixels are still useful in many applications. Previous work [7] examined different readout circuits for the 3T-APS, using MOS devices available in this CMOS technology [8]. However, only DC sweep simulations were carried out, evaluating the voltage swing and linearity of several pixel configurations.

The Sky130 is a mature, 180nm-130nm hybrid technology, which garnered interest in recent years due to the launch of its open-access PDK, developed for use with open source design tools [8].

This paper builds upon previously reported results, introducing detailed layout for four of the six pixel configurations given in [7]. The layouts were drawn and extracted for simulation with open source tools, namely Magic and KLayout. The capacitance of the extracted pixels was simulated using the photodiode model available in the PDK, and transient simulations were carried out for a reduced 2x2 pixel matrix containing one of each pixel to be evaluated, allowing the transient responses of the four different pixel configurations to be evaluated. The open tool NGSPICE was used for simulations.

The rest of this paper contains four sections. In Section II, the 3T structure is described, and the pixel layouts for the different configurations are presented in Section III, as well as the reduced pixel matrix. In Section IV, simulation results are detailed. Finally, the conclusions are presented in Section V.

II. THE 3T PIXEL STRUCTURE

The basic 3T pixel structure is depicted in Fig. 1. It contains, besides the photodiode, a reset transistor (M_{RST}), a readout transistor (M_{SF}) and a row selection transistor (M_{SEL}). A biasing transistor, M_B , is placed in the bottom of each column of the pixel matrix, acting as a current source. M_{SEL} acts as an electronic switch: when ON ($V_{SEL}=\text{HIGH}$) it selects one specific pixel of the column. Neglecting the effect of 'ON' resistance of M_{SEL} , M_{SF} and M_B compose a typical source follower (SF) circuit, hence the naming of readout transistor as M_{SF} . Since the three transistors share the same substrate, the bodies of all of them are grounded, and omitted in the figure.

When a HIGH level Reset pulse is applied on the gate of M_{RST} , the junction capacitance of the reverse biased photodiode is charged, and v_{PIX} goes to $v_{RESET} - V_{tn}(M_{RST})$, where $V_{tn}(M_{RST})$ is the threshold voltage of M_{RST} and v_{RESET} is the voltage at the M_{RST} gate. The use of an NMOS device reduces the maximum possible v_{PIX} (e.g. the dynamic range), in exchange for greater fill factor, since a PMOS would require an N-well.

After Reset goes LOW, the collected photocurrent discharges the diode capacitance. At any given moment the output pixel voltage, v_{OUT} , is given by

$$v_{OUT} = v_{PIX} - V_{sat,SF} - V_{tn,SF} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. 3T-APS structure.

Where $V_{sat,SF}$ and $V_{tn,SF}$ are, respectively, the saturation voltage and the threshold voltage of M_{SF} . Ideally $v_{PIX} - v_{OUT}$ (the SF offset voltage) should remain constant, but several factors (e.g. the body effect on $V_{tn,SF}$) lead the offset voltage to vary over the entire excursion of v_{OUT} , introducing a non-linear distortion. Thus, a nonlinear relation between v_{OUT} and v_{PIX} occurs.

The maximum output voltage swing, ΔV_{OUT} , is given by

$$\Delta V_{OUT} = (V_{DD} - V_{tn(RST)} - V_{tn,SF} - V_{sat,SF}) - V_{OV,B} \quad (2)$$

Where $V_{OV,B}$ is the overdrive voltage of the biasing transistor M_B .

The key property of this kind of pixel is that charge is converted to voltage in the capacitance associated with the v_{PIX} node (photo sensing node). The conversion to voltage is characterized by the charge conversion gain, expressed as the voltage change at the output per collected electron [9]. It is inversely proportional to the sensing node capacitance.

Our aim is to extract and characterize the capacitance of the pixel sensing node using the transistor and photodiode model available in the Sky130 process using open source tools and to evaluate the response of four different pixel configurations w.r.t. transient and DC bias conditions.

III. PIXEL LAYOUTS

A layout of a 2×2 array of 3T-APS pixels was designed, using Magic to generate the devices and KLayout for routing. Different layout arrangements were explored for the reset transistor (M_{RST}), readout transistor (M_{SF}) and the row selection transistor (M_{SEL}), based on the available MOS devices in the Sky130 node [10], which include:

- 1.8V NMOS FET (1v8_std): the standard NMOS device for this technology.
- 1.8V low-VT NMOS FET (1v8_lvt): NMOS devices with lower V_{tn} , due to V_{tn} adjust implants.

Fig. 2. Block diagram of the 2×2 matrix.

- 3.0V native NMOS FET (3v3_ntv): the native NMOS devices are constructed by blocking out all V_{tn} implants, leading to devices with very low threshold voltages. For Sky130 process, the minimum channel length for this device is $L = 0.5 \mu m$.
- 5.0V/10.5V NMOS FET (5v0_std): devices capable of supporting $V_{GS(max)} = 5.5 V$, $V_{BS(max)} = -5.5 V$ and $V_{DS(max)} = 11 V$. Minimum $L = 0.5 \mu m$.

Guided by a previous study conducted on the output swing and linearity of six different 3T-APS pixel configurations using this PDK [7], four designs were selected for layout implementation. The four configurations selected are described in Table I, where the device type and its respective aspect ratios are shown for M_{RST} , M_{SF} and M_{SEL} . A block diagram of the 2×2 matrix is shown in Fig. 2.

TABLE I
TRANSISTOR MODELS OF EACH CONFIGURATION

config.	M_{RST}	M_{SF}	M_{SEL}
I	1v8_std (1/0.2) ^a	1v8_std (1/0.4)	1v8_std (1/0.2)
II	1v8_lvt (1/0.2)	1v8_lvt (1/0.4)	1v8_lvt (1/0.2)
III	1v8_lvt (1/0.2)	3v3_ntv (1/0.5)	5v0_std (1/0.5)
IV	5v0_std (1/0.5)	5v0_std (1/0.5)	5v0_std (1/0.5)

^aAspect ratio (W/L) in ($\mu m / \mu m$).

Table II shows the values for supply voltage, V_{DD} , the high level voltage for V_{RESET} and V_{SEL} .

The layout of the 2×2 pixel matrix, along with the 2-to-1 multiplexer and bias transistors, is shown in Fig. 3. The multiplexer uses 1.8V NMOS FET with an aspect ratio of $1 \mu m / 0.2 \mu m$. For the current mirror used in the bias circuit, 5.0V/10.5V NMOS FET were used with an aspect ratio of $1 \mu m / 0.5 \mu m$. The photodiode was implemented as a

Fig. 3. Layout of the 2x2 pixel array including the 2-to-1 multiplexer and biasing transistors.

$4 \mu\text{m} \times 4 \mu\text{m}$ square, resulting in a total area of $16 \mu\text{m}^2$ and a perimeter of $16 \mu\text{m}$.

Since the Sky130 process node includes five metal layers, Metal 5 (the topmost metal layer) was reserved to cover the non-photosensitive area, and is not shown here, for clarity. Metal 3 and Metal 4 were prioritized for signal buses due to their lower sheet resistance compared to Metal 1 and Metal 2. Fig. 4 details the layout of the pixel in configuration I. The layouts for the other configurations follow a similar structure. Table III shows the photosensitive area, total area and the fill factor obtained for each configuration.

TABLE II
HIGH VOLTAGE LEVELS OF EACH CONFIGURATION

config.	V_{DD} (V)	V_{RESET} (V)	V_{SEL} (V)
I	1.8	1.8	1.8
II	1.8	1.8	1.8
III	1.8	1.8	3.3
IV	3.3	3.3	3.3

TABLE III
FILL FACTOR OF EACH CONFIGURATION

config.	Photosensitive area (μm^2)	Total area (μm^2)	Fill factor
I	158.016	225	70.23 %
II	158.016	225	70.23 %
III	156.186	225	69.42 %
IV	149.994	225	66.66 %

Fig. 4. Detailed layout view of the 3T-APS pixel for Configuration I.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

A simulation of the 2x2 3T-APS pixel array circuit extracted from the layout was carried out in NGSPICE with the goal of characterizing the photodiode capacitance under different operating points, as well as analyzing the multiplexer output waveforms as a function of the voltage across the photodiode.

A. Photodiode Capacitance Characterization

In order to extract the capacitance of the photo sensing node in the 3T-APS, AC simulations were performed for each of the four pixel configurations under study. An AC signal of 1 kHz was injected at the V_{PIX} node, and the resulting current through the AC source was measured. The capacitance is given by

$$C = \frac{10^{I_{dB}/20} \cdot \sin \phi_I}{2\pi \cdot f \cdot V_{PIX}} \quad (3)$$

where I_{dB} and ϕ_I are the magnitude (in dB) and phase of the current through the source, respectively, f is the frequency of the AC signal, and V_{PIX} is the magnitude of the AC voltage signal.

Additionally, the DC level of V_{PIX} was swept to analyze the behavior of the capacitance as a function of bias. The results are presented in Fig. 5.

B. Transient Analysis of the 2x2 Pixel Array

The 2x2 pixel array was simulated with the 2-to-1 multiplexer and bias transistors. The Fig. 6 shows the multiplexer output during the transient analysis. The row and column selection logic was adjusted to display the output of each configuration at $1 \mu\text{s}$ intervals.

Each pixel is reset at $0.25 \mu\text{s}$, and the discharge, simulated by a constant current source connected in parallel with the photodiode, occurs over $0.75 \mu\text{s}$. In Fig. 7 the voltage across the photodiode during each discharge cycle are presented. The constant photocurrent was 22 nA for Config. I, 23 nA for Config. II and III, and 29.5 nA for Config. IV, chosen to discharge the photodiode within $0.75 \mu\text{s}$.

Fig. 5. Photodiode capacitance as function of bias voltage.

Fig. 6. Transient result for the MUX output.

Fig. 7. Transient responses for photodiode reverse voltages.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the capacitance of the photo sensing pixels designed using the Sky130 PDK was obtained through circuit extraction and AC simulations in NGSPICE. Additionally, the full layout of four 3T-APS pixels, designed using Magic and KLayout, is presented as well as the transient response of the 2x2 pixel matrix.

The capacitance of the sense node, obtained from each of the four pixels, is similar and on the order of a few tens of femtofarads. The configurations using 1.8 V transistors presented the highest capacitance values when compared to those using 5.0 V transistors. In all configurations, the capacitance decreases with increasing voltage, as expected, since a higher reverse bias across the photodiode leads to an increase in the depletion region, and the photodiode junction capacitance is dominant over all others in the sensing site. However, an atypical behavior was observed in the configuration that uses a native transistor, in which the capacitance begins to increase when the voltage across the photodiode exceeds 1.3 V, due to the bias change in the readout transistors. This behavior conflicts with linearity requirements when using this configuration.

The transient simulation reveals that using a 1.8 V low-threshold voltage transistor (Config. II) results in a higher output voltage swing compared to Config. I, without affecting the fill factor. Likewise, the use of the native transistor and the 5.0 V transistor also leads to an increase in the output voltage swing, without significantly compromising the fill factor.

This work demonstrates that it is possible to use the open-source tools available for working with the Sky130 PDK to design CMOS imagers. As a next step, the design of an output amplifier is the focus of our future work, as we continue the development of a complete APS chip.

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